

ON SYNTHETIC COUMARINS. PART I. COUMARINS DERIVED FROM RESACETOPHENONE.

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Pechmann's synthesis of coumarins (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119 *et seq*) from phenols and malic acid or acetoacetic ester is of a very general application and a large number of substituted coumarins have been synthesised using different phenols. Resorcinol under these conditions using malic acid gives 7-hydroxy-coumarin or umbelliferone, but coumarins derived from resacetophenone have not yet been prepared. Weiss and Woldich (*Monatsh.*, 1926, 47, 427) however, condensed resacetophenone with ethyl ethoxy-methyleneacetoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide and got a product which later on was found to be 7-hydroxy-3:6-diacetylcoumarin by Weiss and Merksammer (*Monatsh.*, 1928, 50, 115).

In connection with the synthesis of cuscatalin, a coumarin derivative isolated from the stems of *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb. by the present authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 384, 586) it was found necessary to prepare 6-acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin. Recourse was taken to attempt nuclear acetylation through Friedel and Craft's reaction using coumarin or umbelliferone, but was not met with success. Hence substituted coumarins were prepared by the method of Pechmann (*loc. cit.*) starting with resacetophenone. Various condensing agents were employed but it was found that sulphuric acid or fused zinc chloride gives very poor yields, whereas sodium ethoxide was found to be the best for ethyl acetoacetate. In the case of substituted ethyl acetoacetates, if the reaction was done at low temperatures the yield obtained even with concentrated sulphuric acid was quite significant.

Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2016) showed that the substituent group present in the nucleus of the phenol taking part in Pechmann's condensation greatly affects the reaction. He found that chlorophenol reacts with difficulty and gives a very poor yield; whereas a negative substituent like NO_2 or COOH totally inhibits the condensation. Chakravarti and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622), however, proved that these generalisations of Clayton do not hold and they could smoothly condense chlororesorcinol or nitroresorcinol with alkyl-acetoacetic esters both in presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. Clayton (*loc. cit.*) concluded that a negative substituent present in the

neighbourhood of the hydroxyl of the phenol, not taking part in the condensation, has an inhibitive effect on the reaction. In resacetophenone the acetyl group is present in *ortho* position to the free hydroxyl group not taking part in the condensation and being sufficiently acidic does not make the phenol inert even if concentrated sulphuric acid is used as a condensing agent. But if this hydroxyl is surrounded by another hydroxyl group on the other side, as for example in gallacetophenone, condensation does not occur. These facts clearly show that the conclusions of Clayton are not of general application, for according to his views gallacetophenone should have condensed more easily than resacetophenone to form coumarins.

In the present paper resacetophenone has been condensed with malic acid, ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl methylacetoacetate, ethylethyl acetoacetate, ethyl *isopropyl*acetoacetate and ethyl benzylacetoacetate. The acetyl derivative, oxime, semicarbazone and phenylhydrazone of 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, derived from resacetophenone and ethyl acetoacetate, have also been prepared. The methyl group present in the acetyl radical of this coumarin being in the immediate neighbourhood of a carbonyl group is highly reactive and can condense with aromatic aldehydes by the method of Kostanecki and Tambor (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 773, 779) to form styryl ketones, analogous to chalcones derived from resacetophenone. Benzaldehyde has been condensed with 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin in this way to give 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-styrylketone and this interesting compound, which is much more coloured than the corresponding chalcones, gave all the reactions of chalcones. It is proposed to call this class of compounds coumaro-chalcones. Further work on these coumaro-chalcones is in progress and will be communicated shortly.

EXPERIMENTAL.

7-Hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin.—Resacetophenone (1 g.), malic acid (0.85 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (4 g.) were warmed on an oil-bath till no effervescence took place. The mixture was left overnight and then poured over crushed ice. This was repeatedly extracted with chloroform and the chloroform extracts on concentration gave the coumarin as yellowish white amorphous mass. It was recrystallised from benzene and petroleum ether mixture as colourless flakes, m. p. 139°, yield 30%. (Found: C, 64.51; H, 4.20. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.7; H 3.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin.—Resacetophenone (10 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (7.5 g.) and (3 g.) of sodium in 35 c.c. of absolute alcohol

were refluxed over a water-bath for 4 hours, when the sodium salt of the coumarin began to separate gradually and the dark red colour of the reaction mixture faded to fluorescent pink. It was left overnight and then treated with distilled water, when a clear solution was obtained. On acidification a brown oil separated on the top, which was extracted with ether. The ethereal extracts were dehydrated and the solvent evaporated gradually when beautiful needles separated out, m.p. 140°. On recrystallisation from benzene buff coloured star-shaped needles were obtained, m.p. 147°, yield 90%. It is soluble in ether, ethyl acetate, alcohol, pyridine and glacial acetic acid, less so in benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. It gives a very light yellow colour with caustic alkalis and a purple violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 4.91. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.6 per cent).

Resacetophenone (0.7 g.) ethyl acetoacetate (0.65 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.) were set aside overnight and worked up according to the method of Pechmann (*loc. cit.*). The yield obtained was very poor but could be considerably improved if the reaction mixture was left in a frigidaire. Buff coloured needles from benzene, m. p. 146°, were obtained.

The Acetyl derivative.—The above coumarin (0.8 g.), acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and a few drops of pyridine were refluxed over a sand-bath and then decomposed with water. Colourless microcrystalline needles from alcohol were obtained, m.p. 120–21°. (Found: C, 64.05; H, 4.9. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 64.6; H 4.6 per cent). Fused sodium acetate in place of pyridine led to uncrystallisable products.

The Oxime.—The coumarin (0.8 g.), dissolved in alcohol (25 c.c.), was heated with a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) in water (10 c.c.) and 0.6 g. of caustic potash in 5 c.c. of water over a water-bath for 3 hours. On distilling back the solvent and adding ice-cold water the oxime separated out as a white powder which on recrystallisation from ethyl alcohol gave white flakes, m.p. 205°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.0 per cent).

The Semicarbazone, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from petroleum ether as shining colourless flakes, m.p. 183°. (Found: N, 15.88. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.3 per cent).

The Phenylhydrazone, prepared from phenylhydrazine and the coumarin in acetic acid, crystallised from acetic acid as pale yellow needles, m.p. 146–47°. (Found: N, 8.6. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.1 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-3:4-dimethylcoumarin.—Resacetophenone (1 g.) ethyl methylacetoacetate (0.95 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.) were left overnight in a frigidaire at 5°. The mixture was then poured

over crushed ice when an oil separated out which was taken up by ether. On removal of ether a brown crystalline mass was obtained which on recrystallisation from ethyl alcohol gave colourless silky needles, m.p. 168°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 66.75; H, 5.62. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.2 per cent).

7-*Hydroxy-6-acetyl-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin*.—Resacetophenone (1.5 g.), ethyl ethylacetoacetate (1.2 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c.c.) were left in the frigidaire and treated as above. On recrystallisation from alcohol-ether mixture colourless slender shining needles were obtained, m.p. 122°, yield 40%. (Found: C, 68.0; H 5.5. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.3; H 5.7 per cent).

7-*Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-3-isopropylcoumarin*.—Resacetophenone (1.2 g.), ethyl isopropylacetoacetate (1.2 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c. c.) were treated as above. The chloroform extract gave a crystalline yellowish white stuff which on recrystallisation from ether gave clusters of soft colourless needles, m. p. 108° after previous softening at 100°, yield 20%. (Found: C, 68.75; H, 6.0. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.1 per cent).

7-*Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-3-benzylcoumarin*.—Resacetophenone (1 g.), ethyl benzylacetoacetate (1.2 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) were left overnight in the frigidaire. On pouring the mixture over crushed ice the coumarin separated out as a flocculent yellow precipitate. This was twice crystallised from ethyl alcohol when pale yellow plates, m. p. 176°, were obtained, yield 60%. (Found: C, 73.60; H, 5.52. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.2 per cent).

7-*Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-styryl ketone* or 7-*Hydroxy-4-methylcoumaro-chalkone*.—7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.5 g.) were mixed together in about 5 c. c. of alcohol, free from aldehyde, and treated with aqueous caustic potash (50%, 10 c. c.). The mixture was colourless at first and gradually became very intense yellow. It was left overnight in a warm place and then treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, when a yellow oil separated out which turned into flocculent mass on standing. This was then crystallised twice from 50% dilute acetic acid as bright yellow shining flakes, m.p. 141°, yield 75%. It gives a deep orange yellow colour with caustic alkalis, a delicate violet green colour with ferric chloride and the crystals are turned crimson and yield a yellow solution on adding concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 74.32; H, 4.8. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.4; H, 4.6 per cent).